

27 **Summary**

28 United States global health funding cuts and President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief
29 (PEPFAR) disruption threaten decades of HIV program progress. Modelling projects 60,000 to
30 74,000 excess HIV-related deaths across seven sub-Saharan African countries over five years.
31 Approximately 5.8 million people in sub-Saharan Africa remain virally unsuppressed, including
32 an estimated 388,800 children. Into this setting, lenacapavir, a twice-yearly injectable pre-
33 exposure prophylaxis with near-complete trial efficacy, is being incorporated into national plans
34 before questions of opportunity cost, system capacity, and sustainability have been thoroughly
35 examined.

36 Oral pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) has not achieved population-level impact in Africa despite
37 many billions of dollars invested over more than a decade. Adherence has been the central
38 problem. The 3 million person target for lenacapavir cannot be achieved within key populations
39 alone and delivering to the general population means operating at national incidence levels
40 where efficiency is lowest. At national adult HIV incidence, the number of person-years of
41 prophylaxis required to prevent one infection ranges from 133 in Eswatini to more than 8,000 in
42 Ethiopia. This is far above the 41.5 PURPOSE trial figure and will increase as HIV treatment
43 coverage and suppression expands. Cost-effectiveness models assume delivery in sustained high
44 incidence settings, exclude real-world delivery costs, and have not compared lenacapavir against
45 what the same resources would achieve through antiretroviral therapy and/or other prevention
46 scale-up. Delivery requires specialized training, oral loading doses, pharmacovigilance, and
47 sustained follow-up capacity that most health systems do not currently have. Proposals to build
48 lenacapavir delivery infrastructure using African HIV budgets raise legitimate sustainability
49 questions about who bears the costs and who captures the long-term commercial returns.

50 Treatment remains the foundation of epidemic control. Antiretroviral therapy is the only
51 intervention that simultaneously prevents illness, death, and transmission. Expanding viral
52 suppression should remain the central priority, with lenacapavir evaluated rigorously and
53 deployed selectively in genuinely high-incidence, high-risk settings, under African government
54 direction.

55 **Key messages**

56 **What is already known**

- 57 • Antiretroviral therapy is the most efficient and effective prevention intervention as it is
58 the only one that simultaneously prevents illness, death, and HIV transmission. Each
59 person achieving viral suppression reduces their individual transmission risk to zero
60 while also contributing to reducing community viral by shrinking the pool of infectious
61 individuals driving ongoing incidence.
- 62 • In 2024, only seven African countries have achieved the 95–95–95 diagnosis and
63 suppression treatment targets of 86% of people living with HIV. This leaves 5.8 million
64 people unsuppressed including 388,000 children.
- 65 • Along with treatment, condoms, voluntary medical male circumcision, and harm
66 reduction remain the most cost-effective prevention tools in sub-Saharan Africa.
- 67 • Lenacapavir, a twice-yearly subcutaneous injectable requiring an oral loading dose at
68 initiation and repeated if follow-up is delayed, has demonstrated near-complete efficacy
69 as HIV pre-exposure prophylaxis in high-incidence peri-urban trial communities.

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What this viewpoint adds

- Based on national adult HIV incidence, which is far lower than at trial sites, the number needed to treat to prevent one HIV infection ranges from 133 person-years in Eswatini to more than 8,000 in Ethiopia. This is 3 to 201 times higher than the 41.5 PURPOSE trial figure and will rise further as antiretroviral therapy coverage expands and the background incidence declines. Focusing on higher-risk populations makes sense but it will likely make it harder to reach the 3 million people targeted in current donor-driven plans. It will require considerable effort and resources to create demand and ensure adherence.
- The announced generic acquisition price for injectable lenacapavir has been reported at approximately US\$40-55 per person-year, excluding delivery costs. This is comparable to the costs of annual first-line HIV treatment with generic antiretroviral drugs. Proposals to build lenacapavir delivery infrastructure using African HIV budgets and health system capacity raise unresolved questions about opportunity costs, sustainability, and who captures long-term commercial profits.
- Lenacapavir delivery requires specialized training, oral loading doses, pharmacovigilance, and sustained follow-up capacity at a moment when the new Bureau of Global Health Security and Diplomacy (GHSD) *America First* memoranda of understanding (MOUs) have disrupted the current workforce. In South Africa, Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS) reported that cuts have interrupted services provided by the approximately 8,493 PEPFAR-funded staff involved in the HIV response. Lenacapavir delivery requirements land on health systems already operating at or beyond capacity and this additional program burden is largely unexamined in rollout proposals.

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96 **Why it matters**

- 97 • Antiretroviral therapy is the most efficient and effective HIV prevention intervention.
98 Resources are scarce and contracting. Every dollar not directed toward treatment scale-up
99 carries an opportunity cost that has never been formally calculated.
- 100 • With 5.8 million people in sub-Saharan Africa virally unsuppressed, antiretroviral
101 therapy scale-up remains simultaneously the most urgent unmet clinical need and the
102 likely highest-value prevention investment. Lenacapavir should be deployed selectively
103 in genuinely high-incidence, high-risk populations only after explicit opportunity cost
104 analysis.
- 105 • Donor-driven plans to reach 3 million people with lenacapavir depend on identifying,
106 screening, and retaining high-risk HIV-negative individuals. However, many of the
107 community outreach and follow-up systems required to do this are being dismantled
108 under the *America First* transition. If high-risk populations cannot be reliably identified,
109 the program will be both inefficient and ineffective while diverting resources from
110 treatment scale-up.
- 111 • Billions have been invested in HIV prevention technologies that failed to achieve
112 population-level impact in Africa and the overall impact and opportunity costs have never
113 been fully examined. Lenacapavir deserves rigorous, transparent evaluation against
114 competing priorities before large-scale rollout commits health system capacity that
115 cannot easily be redirected.

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117 **Global health financing crisis and the African HIV response**

118 The international HIV response has been an unprecedented success. However, recent United
119 States global health funding cuts, including reductions to PEPFAR and the dismantling of United
120 States Agency for International Development (USAID), threaten decades of progress toward the
121 2030 United Nations 95–95–95 HIV targets [1-4]. Despite over US\$120 billion invested in
122 Africa and 31.6 million people on antiretroviral therapy globally, in 2024 11 million people
123 living with HIV remain without viral suppression [5,6]. Sub-Saharan Africa accounts for 26
124 million of the global 40.8 million people living with HIV of whom 5.8 million (22%) remain
125 virally unsuppressed. Only seven countries meet the 95–95–95 target [5]. Eastern and Southern
126 Africa illustrate the critical pediatric treatment gap. In 2024, only 61% of children living with
127 HIV in the region were on treatment and an estimated 388,800 (48%) lacked viral suppression.
128 Given the resources available, this represents a fundamental program and moral failure.

129 The global HIV response requires approximately US\$21.9 billion annually by 2030 and only
130 US\$18.7 billion was available in 2024 [5]. A further 19–33% contraction in external health
131 assistance projected by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)
132 for 2025 is expected to widen this gap [7]. Against this backdrop, PEPFAR disruption alone is
133 projected to cause 60,000–74,000 excess HIV-related deaths over five years [1]. Into this setting,
134 the United States (US) government, pharmaceutical companies, multilateral agencies,
135 foundations, and non-profit organizations are advancing lenacapavir rollout plans affecting
136 millions of Africans. In some instances lenacapavir deployment plans were made at the
137 presidential level before African line ministries have completed strategic planning through their
138 own MOU negotiation processes.

139 As part of the push, the Global Fund, Gilead, and PEPFAR have announced a coordinated effort
140 to provide lenacapavir for PrEP to up to 3 million people by 2028 [8,9,10]. This new initiative
141 commits substantial international and country-level implementation capacity to a new
142 prevention approach even as existing programs face ongoing funding constraints [1,3]. These
143 fiscal constraints make it important to consider whether the same resources could have achieved
144 greater impact if directed elsewhere, particularly in high-burden settings where investing in
145 closing treatment gaps and achieving viral suppression would likely prevent more infections,
146 illness, and deaths [11,12].

147 A targeted PubMed search covering January 2025 to January 2026 using the term “lenacapavir”
148 retrieved 152 indexed publications. None questioned whether large-scale rollout should be
149 deprioritized in settings with persistent viral suppression gaps. The same search applied to the
150 Lancet family of journals found that only three of 66 publications examined prioritization against
151 fiscal constraints and unresolved treatment gaps. Full search methods are reported in the
152 companion Lancet Global Health Comment [13]. This absence of critical analysis and discussion
153 is worrisome. The following viewpoint attempts to address these and related questions, drawing
154 on available epidemiological, economic, and health systems evidence (Figure 1). This viewpoint
155 does not question lenacapavir’s efficacy. The PURPOSE trials represent a genuine scientific
156 advance that could benefit many people at high and persistent risk of HIV infection. The
157 discussion here is about sequence, scale, and resource allocation, not about whether lenacapavir
158 works or barriers to access.

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Figure 1: Major challenges to lenacapavir implementation in sub-Saharan Africa

1. *Treatment gap priority*: 5.8 million people lack viral suppression; treatment-as-prevention is epidemiologically superior to PrEP interventions
2. *Funding transition demands co-financing*: US\$9.5 billion annual gap; 60,000-74,000 predicted excess deaths from PEPFAR restructuring
3. *Infrastructure costs exceed drug price*: Fixed implementation costs (staff, facilities, monitoring) persist regardless of pharmaceutical price reductions
4. *No sustainable financing beyond a few years*: Time-limited donor support leaves governments with unsustainable infrastructure commitments
5. *Market-seeding ethics*: Government resources build infrastructure/demand; pharmaceutical companies capture long-term profits (US PrEP precedent)
6. *Opportunity costs*: NNT 1,000-2,000 vs. treatment NNT 1-7.5; cost-effectiveness declines with incidence; vertical programs absorb scarce management capacity
7. *Sovereignty undermined*: Externally-designed rollout structured before African governments completed MOU strategic planning
8. *Vertical fragmentation and complexity contradict integration*: Specialized protocols and parallel systems required when MOUs mandate service integration
9. *Real-world effectiveness unknown*: No evidence on continuation rates, adherence, or population-level impact in African settings
10. *Treatment-prevention institutional dualism*: Artificial separation contradicts evidence that viral suppression prevents transmission; treatment epidemiologically superior prevention intervention and should be priority

168 Oral PrEP experience and lenacapavir effectiveness

169 Oral PrEP delivery in Africa has not matched the promise seen in clinical trials. Annual global
170 investment in HIV prevention research and development reached US\$1.25 billion in 2021, with
171 additional billions invested in drugs, service delivery, and program infrastructure by PEPFAR,
172 the Global Fund, and other donors over the preceding decade [14]. Despite this investment,
173 globally only 3.9 million people were initiating or continuing PrEP in 2024, against a UNAIDS

174 target of 21.2 million for epidemic control [5]. In 2023, 64% of all PrEP users globally were
175 concentrated in just five African countries [5].

176 As in the trials, adherence to oral PrEP has been the central problem. In HIV Prevention Trials
177 Network (HPTN) 082, only about a quarter of participants had drug levels consistent with high
178 adherence by 6 months, falling to fewer than one in five by 12 months [15]. as observed in
179 prospective cohorts from Kenya where persistence fell to 42.9% and 22.9% at 6 and 12 months
180 respectively [16,17]. Population-based studies in rural Kenya, Uganda, and South Africa
181 document similarly low uptake even when PrEP is actively offered through targeted community
182 delivery [18-20]. These challenges have made it difficult for oral PrEP to achieve population-
183 level impact in generalized epidemic settings.

184 While long-acting injectable lenacapavir addresses the daily adherence barrier it poses other
185 implementation challenges. The PURPOSE 1 trial recorded 100% efficacy among 2,134
186 cisgender women, and PURPOSE 2 recorded 99.9% efficacy among men and gender-diverse
187 individuals at background incidences of approximately 2.4 per 100 person-years [21,22]. In July
188 2025, World Health Organization (WHO) recommended injectable lenacapavir twice yearly as
189 an additional HIV-prevention option within combination prevention approaches [23]. However,
190 the guidelines did not specify a minimum background-incidence threshold. The US list price of
191 US\$28,000 per person-year is noted for context only. All analyses exclude delivery costs and use
192 the approximately US\$40 generic price cited in supplier agreements [24].

193 **Lenacapavir and the prevention hierarchy: placing a promising tool in its proper order**

194 For decades, HIV treatment and prevention have been planned, financed, and delivered through
195 largely separate program structures [25-27]. This divide was not accidental. It was purposefully
196 built into funding streams, institutional mandates, staffing, targets, and planning processes to

197 control and shape how priorities were set [25-27]. As a result, decisions about resources were
198 often made within these silos rather than across them. This effectively limited direct comparison
199 between treatment and other prevention interventions [25-27]. The separation was reinforced by
200 parallel scientific and advocacy communities including prevention-focused research agendas that
201 did not fully incorporate treatment as prevention. This conceptual and structural division was
202 maintained even as evidence for its impact began to emerge. As part of this artificial divide, in
203 2014 the inaugural HIV Research for Prevention (HIVR4P) conference in South Africa devoted
204 its program predominantly to vaccines, antibodies, and PrEP [28]. This manufactured gap
205 between prevention and treatment has persisted in scientific and policy discourse to the present
206 day.

207 Early proposals to use antiretroviral therapy to curb transmission were actively resisted even as
208 ecological studies showed that treatment scale-up was associated with falling incidence and
209 observational studies documented corresponding declines in incidence [11,29]. HIV scientific
210 leadership questioned whether the epidemiological evidence was sufficient to justify a
211 fundamental reorientation of prevention strategy [30-32]. As a result, treatment was not
212 consistently considered alongside other prevention options in strategic planning for the HIV
213 response. Additionally, until 2015 WHO HIV and TB treatment recommendations focused only
214 on clinical criteria relying on a test and wait until severely immunocompromised strategy,
215 ignoring the increasing evidence regarding the benefits of earlier treatment for prevention of
216 illness and transmission. Decades of deliberately keeping treatment and prevention in separate
217 programmatic silos have imposed enormous costs that have never been formally quantified. This
218 artificial divide contributed to the chronic misallocation of scarce resources, with the delay in
219 treatment scale-up likely resulting in millions of preventable HIV infections, illnesses, and
220 deaths [29].

221 Resources are scarce, treatment gaps remain enormous, and lenacapavir advocates have largely
222 sidestepped where injectable PrEP belongs in a rational prevention hierarchy. The UNAIDS
223 press statement of 15 April 2026 welcoming the expanded 3 million person lenacapavir
224 commitment illustrates this precisely as it cites 1.3 million new HIV infections per year as the
225 rationale for accelerated investment but contains no mention of treatment, viral suppression gaps,
226 or the 5.8 million people in sub-Saharan Africa already living with HIV without suppression
227 [33]. The same press statement invokes the UNAIDS Global AIDS Strategy 2026–2031, which
228 sets a 2030 target of 20 million people on antiretroviral (ARV) -based prevention including
229 lenacapavir while the treatment target is 40 million people virally suppressed. This illustrates the
230 dualistic thinking. If 40 million people are on treatment and virally suppressed, incidence would
231 be extremely low and lenacapavir would not be needed at scale [34]. Scaling from 3 million to
232 20 million on lenacapavir alone, in a contracting resource environment, has not been costed
233 against what those same resources would achieve if directed toward closing the treatment gap.

234 Antiretroviral therapy sits at the top of the priority list. It is the only intervention that
235 simultaneously prevents illness, death, and transmission. Montaner and colleagues made the case
236 for expanding antiretroviral therapy (ART) to curb epidemic growth in the Lancet in 2006 [11]
237 and in 2008 other scientists extended this argument to universal testing and immediate treatment
238 to eliminate HIV in South Africa [29]. The Rakai cohort established in 2000 that transmission
239 was directly related to viral load and rare among individuals with undetectable levels [35].
240 HPTN 052 confirmed in 2011 that immediate ART reduced transmission by 96% among
241 serodiscordant couples [36]. The PARTNER 1 and 2 studies documented zero transmissions
242 across more than 126,000 condomless sex acts when viral load was undetectable, reporting in
243 2016 and 2019 respectively [12,37]. Each person achieving viral suppression eliminates

244 transmission risk entirely while gaining years of healthy life. No other intervention delivers this
245 combination.

246 Condoms, voluntary medical male circumcision, and harm reduction occupy the second tier.
247 Condom promotion has contributed to substantial incidence reductions in high-burden African
248 settings [38]. Voluntary medical male circumcision (VMMC) provides approximately 60%
249 protection against male HIV acquisition from a single lifetime intervention and is among the
250 most cost-effective prevention investments available [39]. Harm reduction is the evidence-based
251 foundation for HIV prevention among people who inject drugs [40]. All three are chronically
252 under-resourced relative to their epidemiological contribution and conspicuously absent from
253 most lenacapavir advocacy documents.

254 PrEP, including lenacapavir, occupies a distinct and more limited tier. It protects individuals who
255 are not infected with HIV against future infection but does not reduce the pool of people
256 transmitting the virus. It works best among people at high risk of infection including sex
257 workers, people who inject drugs, men who have sex with men in high-burden communities, and
258 individuals in serodiscordant partnerships where the HIV-positive partner is not virally
259 suppressed. In sub-Saharan Africa, however, an estimated 75% of new HIV infections occur
260 outside these key populations among the general heterosexual population [41]. Reaching 3
261 million people with lenacapavir cannot be achieved within key populations alone. However,
262 extending coverage into the general population means operating at national-average incidence,
263 where numbers needed to treat (NNTs) are highest and cost-effectiveness is weakest.

264 Additionally, where viral suppression is achieved, Undetectable = Untransmittable (U=U)
265 already eliminates transmission risk and PrEP adds little additional impact. Lenacapavir belongs

266 in this tier, deployed selectively, not promoted as a population-level intervention where the
267 treatment gap remains the primary driver of ongoing transmission.

268 Donor power distorts the prevention hierarchy and resource prioritization process. Funders,
269 maintaining the flawed prevention-treatment dualism, can question priorities publicly while
270 recipient country program staff and government officials often cannot. When interventions arrive
271 as part of aid packages, sometimes at the presidential level, the ability to decline or openly
272 debate the terms is limited. This inequity may help explain why donor-driven PrEP-specific
273 research and development (R&D) funding reached US\$270 million in 2021 (the PrEP component
274 of the broader prevention R&D envelope), a two-fold increase and the highest level since
275 tracking began, while treatment-as-prevention, condoms, VMMC, and harm reduction remained
276 comparatively underfunded despite superior or equivalent population-level impact [14]. It also
277 helps explain why, to our knowledge, no published analysis has questioned whether lenacapavir
278 should be deprioritized in settings with large treatment gaps to allow for focus on reaching
279 people with treatment. When difficult trade-offs cannot be examined openly, resource allocation
280 decisions proceed without adequate critical analysis.

281 African program colleagues contributed substantively to the arguments in this viewpoint. Most
282 did not appear as named authors. That decision reflects the professional risk of publicly
283 questioning a direction that major funders have already endorsed. When careers and institutions
284 depend on continued donor relationships, the pressure not to challenge prevailing priorities is
285 real and rarely stated. That pressure is itself a form of distortion in the evidence base.

286 Prioritization across the hierarchy of interventions is critical. Resources are contracting and
287 health systems are under severe strain. The *America First* transition is forcing African
288 governments to reassess how they can achieve health targets and what they can actually sustain.

289 When resources were abundant, keeping treatment and other prevention in separate silos without
290 considering the hierarchy was wasteful. When resources are scarce, it is dangerous. Prevention
291 spending has rarely had to justify itself against treatment within a single resource allocation
292 process. This has to change.

293 **From trial to service delivery and impact: lenacapavir's number needed to treat blind spot**

294 The impact of any prevention intervention is directly proportional to the effectiveness and the
295 background incidence of the condition it targets. Where incidence and effectiveness are high, the
296 NNT is low and the intervention is efficient. Where incidence is low, more people must receive
297 the intervention to prevent each infection and costs rise accordingly. The NNT for lenacapavir
298 represents the number of person-years of prophylaxis required to prevent one HIV infection,
299 calculated as 100 divided by background incidence per 100 person-years assuming 100%
300 efficacy. The distinction between prevention and treatment NNTs matters. Each person-year of
301 lenacapavir is delivered to an HIV-negative individual who may never have been infected
302 regardless. Each person-year of ART delivers clinical benefit and transmission elimination to
303 someone already living with the virus.

304 Reducing the number of people living with HIV who are not virally suppressed through
305 treatment scale-up has a direct impact on NNT. At the PURPOSE 1 background incidence of
306 24.1 per 1000 person-years, the NNT is approximately 41.5 person-years (Figure 1). Even at this
307 relatively high background incidence, achieving this level of efficiency would require restricting
308 access to individuals at very high risk and approaching near-perfect effectiveness as an NNT of
309 41.5 remains relatively high for HIV programmes. This incidence and NNT figure reflects peri-
310 urban, high-incidence trial communities and does not represent national program conditions. As
311 treatment access improves and/or HIV incidence declines, the NNT rises to dramatically (Table

312 1). These are not hypothetical projections. They are the expected consequence of successful ART
 313 scale-up.

314 **Figure 2: National HIV incidence per 1000 uninfected adults 15-49, PEPFAR/GHSD**
 315 **bilateral countries (2024)**

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Source: UNAIDS 2024 AIDSinfo. $NNT = 100 \div \text{incidence per 100 person-years}$, assuming 100% efficacy. Real-world NNTs will be higher as treatment coverage expands. Liberia: estimate not available.

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319 UNAIDS 2024 incidence estimates for adults aged 15–49 across PEPFAR bilateral countries
 320 range from 7.5 per 1,000 in Eswatini to 0.12 per 1,000 in Ethiopia [42] (Table 1). The PURPOSE
 321 trial background incidence of 24.1 per 1,000 is more than three times higher than even the most
 322 burdened PEPFAR country. National adult incidence is not equivalent to incidence in the high-
 323 risk subpopulations enrolled in trials. We use it here as an illustrative lower bound rather than a

324 programmatic target. The critical question is not whether high-risk individuals exist within each
 325 country but whether they can be identified, reached, and retained at a scale of 3 million across
 326 generalised African epidemics. Systematic delivery to genuinely high-risk populations at that
 327 scale has not been achieved for any HIV prevention intervention in sub-Saharan Africa. Even at
 328 the PURPOSE trial incidence of 24.1 per 1,000, an NNT of 41.5 person-years requires near-
 329 perfect risk stratification and retention. The infrastructure to achieve this systematically has not
 330 been demonstrated.

331 **Table 1. Illustrative number needed to treat (person-years of prophylaxis delivery) to prevent one**
 332 **HIV infection at national adult HIV incidence levels, PEPFAR bilateral countries**

Country / setting	Incidence per 1,000 adults 15–49 (UNAIDS 2024)	Incidence per 100 Person Years	NNT (person- years)	vs PURPOSE trial
PURPOSE trial (background)	24.1	2.41	41.5	1× (reference)
Eswatini	7.5	0.750	133	3×
South Africa	5.3	0.530	189	5×
Mozambique	4.9	0.490	204	5×
Lesotho	3.1	0.310	323	8×
Botswana	3.1	0.310	323	8×
Zambia	2.8	0.280	357	9×
Namibia	2.6	0.260	385	9×
Zimbabwe	1.4	0.140	714	17×
Uganda	1.4	0.140	714	17×

Tanzania	1.1	0.110	909	22×
Malawi	0.92	0.092	1,087	26×
Angola	0.89	0.089	1,124	27×
South Sudan	0.80	0.080	1,250	30×
Ghana	0.79	0.079	1,266	31×
Cameroon	0.70	0.070	1,429	34×
Kenya	0.53	0.053	1,887	45×
DRC	0.29	0.029	3,448	83×
Rwanda	0.29	0.029	3,448	83×
Nigeria	0.26	0.026	3,846	93×
Ethiopia	0.12	0.012	8,333	201×

333 *NNT = 100 ÷ incidence per 100 person-years (PY), assuming 100% lenacapavir efficacy; real-world NNTs will be*
334 *higher. These are illustrative population-average estimates based on national adult HIV incidence. Real-world*
335 *NNTs would be higher if effectiveness were lower than in trials, but lower if delivery were concentrated in*
336 *subpopulations with incidence above the national adult average. Source: UNAIDS 2024 HIV incidence rate per*
337 *1,000 uninfected adults 15–49, AIDSinfo [42]. Liberia: UNAIDS 2024 estimate not available.*

338 At national incidence rates, NNTs range from 133 person-years in Eswatini to more than 8,000
339 in Ethiopia, 3 to 201 times the PURPOSE trial figure (Table 1). Real-world effectiveness below
340 100%, sub-optimal retention, and rising treatment coverage will push these figures higher still.
341 This is in stark contrast with antiretroviral therapy. In serodiscordant couple studies, viral
342 suppression eliminates transmission risk [12, 32, 35, 36, 37, 43], implying that each person-year
343 of effective treatment among virally unsuppressed individuals yields an NNT on the order of 1 to
344 13 person-years. The range is based on serodiscordant couple studies demonstrating that viral
345 suppression eliminates sexual transmission risk entirely, and on mathematical modelling
346 showing that each person achieving suppression prevents between 1 and 7 or more onward
347 infections depending on the local reproductive number [29]. This is an estimate, but it is likely

348 directionally correct and far below any lenacapavir NNT at national incidence. To our
349 knowledge, no published analysis compares program-level lenacapavir NNTs against what the
350 same resources would achieve by closing the viral suppression gap, where each additional person
351 reaching suppression gains years of healthy life and eliminates their transmission risk entirely.
352 We have been unable to find published plans or guidance that make these trade-offs explicit.

353 **Health system complexity and management bandwidth**

354 The WHO African Region has only 1.55 physicians, nurses, and midwives per 1,000 population
355 against a minimum of 4.45 needed for essential services [44]. PEPFAR supported 342,000 health
356 workers in 2024. As the partner-based model unwinds, South Africa has already lost over 8000
357 healthcare workers and Kenya, Malawi, and Mozambique face similar reductions [45]. Countries
358 such as South Africa, Botswana, and Namibia may lose bilateral US HIV support entirely as
359 *America First* agreements progress. Other countries such as Zimbabwe and Zambia have refused
360 to sign the MOUs. Every dollar counts and there is no room for inefficiency or ineffectiveness.

361 As vertical HIV programmes shrink under funding constraints, integrating HIV services into
362 primary health care is both the more efficient path and the more sustainable one [2]. Lenacapavir
363 rollout complicates that transition as it competes with core HIV programme functions that need
364 to be reduced in number, simplified, and integrated into routine primary care. Lenacapavir
365 delivery requires specialized training for injection technique, candidate identification,
366 counselling, pharmacovigilance, adverse event monitoring, HIV testing, and follow-up. These
367 demands already exceed what the current workforce can meet for existing services. Rolling out
368 lenacapavir to millions of people before African governments have completed their own strategic
369 planning adds a new vertical programme at precisely the moment when simplification and
370 integration are required. The decision to proceed appears to have been made without a thorough

371 assessment of opportunity costs or meaningful consultation with line ministries, potentially
372 undermining the sovereignty that the America First MOUs claim to want to restore.

373 **Commercial incentives and ethical tensions**

374 The US rollout of oral PrEP illustrates how public investment can be leveraged to build markets
375 to generate private returns. After its launch in 2019, the U.S. *Ending the HIV Epidemic* initiative
376 grew to about \$573 million annually, supporting health center networks, clinician training,
377 laboratory systems, and demand generation [46]. While improving access to oral PrEP for some
378 communities, the investment created the market upon which Gilead's oral PrEP products
379 flourished. Since Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approval of Truvada for PrEP in 2012,
380 Gilead's estimated U.S. PrEP-related revenues have likely exceeded US\$10 billion, including
381 more than US\$1.8 billion in combined Truvada and Descovy sales reported in 2023 legal
382 proceedings alone [47-49]. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) scientists
383 developed the PrEP regimen and taxpayers funded an estimated US\$143 million in foundational
384 research. Gilead nonetheless successfully resisted the government's 2019 patent infringement
385 lawsuit and the Department of Justice (DOJ) abandoned its appeal in January 2025 [48, 50].
386 While expanding access to diagnosis and treatment was included in Ending the HIV Epidemic
387 (EHE) as one of the pillars alongside PrEP, the latest data available from 2022 indicates that the
388 US still has an estimated 516,000 (43%) people who are virally unsuppressed [51]. This pattern
389 highlights how public investment can de-risk innovation, build markets, and skew prevention
390 priorities while the private sector collects the profits.

391 Proposals to finance lenacapavir market development through African HIV and health budgets
392 risk replicating this extractive model. The United States government will subsidize African
393 access to Gilead's lenacapavir through donor financing, infrastructure investment, and demand

394 generation. When this time-limited support ends, procurement backing and low-cost pricing
395 commitments may go with it leaving African governments to cover the costs. Gilead and its
396 commercial licensees will be in position to reap the profits from the newly established markets.
397 Voluntary licensing agreements have made generic lenacapavir available at approximately
398 US\$40 per person-year in low-income countries. However, generic licensing and time-limited
399 no-profit commitments do not resolve who bears the long-term costs of drugs, supply chains, and
400 delivery systems. Even discounted pricing is not necessarily a bargain, as it likely incorporates
401 recovery of research and development investments over time. Once people are started on
402 lenacapavir, governments may face difficult choices about continuing treatment, especially as
403 donor support becomes less certain. Continue funding a drug with limited population-level
404 impact at national scale or withdraw support from those already depending on it. That choice
405 should not be imposed on African health systems that cannot yet afford to treat all people living
406 with HIV.

407 **Cost-effectiveness modelling: unrealistic assumptions**

408 UNAIDS and other modelling suggests lenacapavir could be cost-effective in high-incidence
409 settings at the US \$40 generic price but only under assumptions that do not reflect real-world
410 epidemic dynamics [52]. The models assume sustained high incidence concentrated in
411 identifiable high-risk populations, optimal implementation, and constant incidence trajectories
412 that ignore the declines expected as treatment coverage expands. Successful ART scale-up
413 drives incidence below the 1% threshold at which UNAIDS modelling suggests lenacapavir
414 ceases to be cost-saving [52] making the intervention progressively less necessary precisely as
415 HIV programmes achieve their goals. They also exclude delivery costs including the loading-
416 dose expenses that UNAIDS acknowledges may represent 20–50% of total provision cost for
417 individuals using lenacapavir for one year or less [52]. This does not represent the actual

418 epidemiology of most PEPFAR bilateral countries, where national incidence is far lower, ART
419 access is increasing with concomitant declining incidence, and genuinely high-risk
420 subpopulations are difficult and costly to reach at scale. Identifying and retaining large numbers
421 of the high-risk populations that make lenacapavir cost-effective has never been achieved in
422 Africa except for testing, treatment, condoms, and VMMC, and we did not identify any
423 published plan that explains how this time will be different. When realistic incidence trajectories,
424 sub-optimal retention, inability to reach high-risk populations at scale, and full delivery costs are
425 factored in together, the cost-effective scope for lenacapavir narrows substantially and will
426 continue to narrow as treatment succeeds [52]. To our knowledge, no published modelling
427 compares lenacapavir against what the same resources would achieve if directed toward ART
428 scale-up, VMMC, condom distribution, or harm reduction [53]. Formal incremental cost-
429 effectiveness analyses comparing lenacapavir against ART scale-up, VMMC, condom
430 promotion, and harm reduction using a common objective function such as disability-adjusted
431 life years (DALYs) averted or HIV infections prevented are needed before large-scale resource
432 commitments are made. Without that comparison, claims of cost-effectiveness are incomplete
433 and potentially misleading.

434 The drug cost comparison is instructive. At US\$40 per person-year, delivering lenacapavir to 3
435 million people costs US\$120 million annually in drug costs alone, before delivery, training,
436 pharmacovigilance, and infrastructure. The same US\$120 million directed toward generic first-
437 line antiretroviral therapy at equivalent cost would treat 3 million virally unsuppressed people,
438 each of whom eliminates their individual transmission risk entirely and gains years of healthy
439 life. Without considering the health gains, the NNT to prevent 1 infection for that investment is
440 on the order of 1 to 13. The NNT for lenacapavir at national incidence across most PEPFAR

441 bilateral countries ranges from 200 to more than 8,000 person-years. No published cost-
442 effectiveness analysis has made this comparison directly.

443 **Real-world effectiveness: learning from history**

444 Lenacapavir is not the first promising HIV prevention technology to face the predictable gap
445 between trial efficacy and real-world impact. The dapivirine vaginal ring, tenofovir gel, and
446 female condoms all demonstrated biological efficacy but failed to achieve population-level
447 impact in sub-Saharan Africa. Insufficient attention to implementation science, premature scale-
448 up, and inadequate community engagement were common factors. Some oral PrEP programs
449 went further. However, when adherence data revealed poor real-world performance, evaluation
450 criteria were quietly shifted toward initiation counts. This obscures reality as it is a metric that
451 programs could report favorably regardless of whether people stayed on PrEP or were protected.
452 Programs looked successful while individual and community-level impact remained limited.

453 Lenacapavir removes the daily pill burden but replaces it with a different set of problems. Before
454 anyone receives lenacapavir, WHO recommends confirmed HIV-negative status and hepatitis B
455 screening, with annual retesting and vaccination for those who test negative [24]. These
456 requirements assume a testing and laboratory infrastructure that most high-burden African
457 settings do not have. Returning every six months for subcutaneous injections is not trivial,
458 particularly for pregnant women and people in remote or under-resourced settings. Injection-site
459 reactions including pain occurred in 68% of PURPOSE trial recipients and trial participants
460 receive incentives to continue that real-world programs cannot match. The oral loading dose
461 required at initiation, and again if the follow-up window is missed, adds an adherence demand
462 the injectable framing tends to obscure. After discontinuation, lenacapavir remains detectable but
463 falls below the protective threshold for months, creating a resistance risk if HIV acquisition

464 occurs during that period. These are not minor details. They are structural vulnerabilities that
465 PrEP history suggests may be overlooked or underreported once programs shift their metrics
466 toward initiation counts.

467 The sexually transmitted infection (STI) burden is a further concern. High STI prevalence and
468 high HIV incidence share common epidemiological drivers in sub-Saharan Africa where the
469 populations most likely to benefit from lenacapavir carry the highest STI burden. Evidence from
470 Zambia, Uganda, and Kenya documents high baseline STI prevalence among people accessing
471 HIV prevention services, and PrEP scale-up in some settings has coincided with increases in
472 bacterial STI diagnoses [54,55,56]. Whether PrEP adoption reduces condom use and STI risk in
473 diverse African heterosexual epidemic settings requires further research, leaving a critical
474 evidence gap at precisely the moment when large-scale rollout is being planned. Lenacapavir
475 offers no protection against STIs. Without sustained condom promotion and STI screening built
476 into programs from the start, lenacapavir rollout risks increasing co-morbidity burdens in health
477 systems already operating beyond capacity. The evidence needed to design effective programmes
478 at scale in African heterosexual epidemic settings, including data on STIs and the programmatic
479 requirements of injectable PrEP, remains limited.

480 Billions of dollars have been invested in many HIV prevention technologies that failed to
481 achieve population-level impact in Africa. For reasons stated above, the opportunity costs were
482 never calculated against what ART scale-up would have achieved with the same resources.
483 Nothing in the current lenacapavir rollout plans suggests the conditions that produced those
484 previous failures have been resolved. The history of HIV prevention technology transfer to
485 Africa is often a history of trial success followed by implementation failure. A different outcome
486 requires a fundamentally different approach to accountability, community engagement,

487 identifying who would most efficiently and effectively benefit, and an honest evaluation of what
488 the money could otherwise buy.

489 **Conclusion**

490 The evidence presented here does not argue against lenacapavir, but rather for clearer
491 prioritization grounded in available data and experience. With 5.8 million people in sub-Saharan
492 Africa virally unsuppressed, treatment scale-up remains the highest-value investment available.
493 It prevents illness, death, and transmission simultaneously at a fraction of the cost and
494 complexity of lenacapavir delivered across population-average incidence settings. Lenacapavir
495 has a role in genuinely high-incidence, high-risk settings where other interventions cannot reach.
496 That role should be defined by African governments through their own strategic planning,
497 informed by country-level NNT analysis, realistic delivery cost estimates, and an honest
498 comparison of what the same resources would achieve if directed toward closing the treatment
499 gap.

500 Country ownership is either substantive or it is rhetorical. Lenacapavir rollout is the first genuine
501 test of whether the *America First* MOU framework means what it claims. African governments
502 must have the authority and analytical support to make these prioritization decisions themselves,
503 free from the commercial interests, donor preferences, and institutional silos that have distorted
504 HIV resource allocation for decades. Ending AIDS depends on African governments having the
505 sovereignty and agency to get these decisions right.

506 **Declaration of interests**

507 The authors declare no competing interests. This analysis received no funding and represents the
508 authors' independent scientific opinion.

509 **Author contributions**

510 Reuben Granich conceptualized, designed, conducted analysis, and wrote the manuscript. Somya
511 Gupta, Isabelle Munyangaju, and Mike Ruffner contributed to the analysis, reviewed and
512 critically revised the manuscript, and approved the final version for submission.

513 **Data availability statement**

514 This viewpoint does not report original empirical data. All epidemiological figures are drawn
515 from publicly available sources cited in the references. The NNT calculations in Table 1 are
516 derived from UNAIDS 2024 HIV incidence rate estimates (AIDSinfo, aidsinfo.unaids.org) and
517 PURPOSE trial background incidence rates reported in references 21 and 22, using the formula
518 $NNT = 100 \div \text{incidence per 100 person-years}$, assuming 100% efficacy. All derived data
519 presented in Table 1 are fully reproducible from the UNAIDS AIDSinfo database
520 (aidsinfo.unaids.org) using the formula and source year stated above.

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